

PREDICTION OF BIDIKMISI GRADUATION USING C ++ BASED ON CODEBLOCK

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ABSTRACT

Bidikmisi student graduation makes its own paradigm for universities that have bidikmisi winning students, because if Bidikmisi students do not graduate with determined conditions it has a very bad impact on university performance and for students themselves. In this study the programming language used is C ++ with the codeblock tool. The results of this study predict the bidikmisi student graduation using C ++ based programming language codeblock is more efficient and effective.

Keyword : Prediction, Graduation, C, Code Block

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The campus is a place where there is an interactive teaching and learning process between lecturers and students with a burden according to the level of education (D3 / S1). Every year student data increases so that it takes a management who can know the level of success of students in attending lectures.

Bidikmisi is a government assistance program issued through the Ministry of Research and Technology of Higher Education for outstanding students but economically disadvantaged. Students who get Bidikmisi Scholarships are required to be better than regular students without the assistance of Bidikmisi scholarships. So that failure in following the lecture process and education in Higher Education, is very necessary to be monitored by management.

Campus Management really needs a data that contains predictions of the graduation of students and will be used to take strategic decisions so that they can handle earlier and reduce the quantity of Droup Out. This graduation prediction can be started when students are still sitting in the initial semester so that the percentage of predictions is higher in accuracy.

Looking at the paradigm above, it is necessary to make a program that will be used to predict the bidikmisi student graduation rate at the Purbaya Tegal Polytechnic Campus.

1.2 Formulation of The Problem

Based on the background above, a problem statement can be drawn on how to determine graduation for students who have won bidikmisi scholarships at the Ministry of Research Technology for Higher Education.

1.3 Objectives and Benefits

The purpose of this study is to provide information to institutions about students who are predicted to graduate and not graduate, so that the institution can quickly make a policy to deal with it early. To fulfill the tasks of Algorithm & Programming Odd Semester Courses and implement Algorithm & Programming Courses

- a. As an institution consideration in taking policy
- b. As input for parents of students and guardians to provide guidance as early as possible

2. LITERATURE

2.1 Related Research

There are several studies on prediction of graduation or achievement using various models / methods as analysis based on historical data:

Diana Laeli and Eko Darmanto, 2014 "Decision support system to predict student graduation using the naïve bayes method". In this study the results achieved have an accuracy for on time of 93% and accuracy for being late at 71% by using the Naïve Bayes method which is increasingly optimal by determining students to graduate on time or late.

Marselina Suhartinah, Ernastuti, 2010 “ Graduation Prediction Of Gunadharma University Studens Using Algorithm Naive Bayes and C45 Algorithm” . The accuracy of the prediction accuracy of C45 is 85.7% with an error value in the study using C45 reaching 14.3%. And testing using the Naive Bayes algorithm gets an accuracy value of 80.85%.

Erman Yukselturk, Turkey, 2012 “ Predicting Dropout Student an Aplication of Data Mining Methods in an Online Education Program”. Datasheet testing uses several algorithms as follows: K-Neirest Neighbor (KNN) gets an accuracy value of 87% using Decision Tree, the accuracy level is 79.7% while using Naive Bayes Algorithm produces 76.8% accuracy and uses Neural Network algorithm produce an accuracy rate of 73.9%. The results above are maximized and produce the greatest accuracy level of 88.02% using Naive Bayes Algorithm with backward selection features.

Prasetyo Andy, Tegal, 2018 “Naïve Bayes Algorithm Based on Forward Selection on Graduation Prediction on Time”. That the addition of the Forward Selection feature in predictions can improve accuracy and enter into the excellent clasification section with an accuracy of 97.92% with a precision level of 98.92% compared to predictions using only the Naive Bayes algorithm of 97.68%.

2.1 Theoretical

Prediction is a process of systematically estimating something that is most likely to happen in the future based on past and present information that is owned, so that errors (the difference between something that happens with the results of estimates) can be minimized.

Bidikmisi is a tuition assistance for prospective students who are not economically capable and have academic potential both to study in higher education in excellent study programs until graduating on time (Ristekdikti, 2014)

C ++ language is an object-oriented programming language to solve problems. Code :: Blocks is a free, non-profit, open-source and cross-platform integrated development environment program (Andy Prasetyo, 2018)

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The stages in this study are as follows:

- a. Data collection
- b. Initial data processing
- c. Grouping
- d. Stages of the proposed method
- e. Experiments and research testing
- f. Research evaluation and validation
- g. Results of research accuracy

The method proposed in this study is CodeBlock Based C ++ Language Programming to predict Bidikmisi student graduation from Purbaya Tegal Polytechnic. Following are the steps in this study:

1. Calculate the assignment value of each student
In one semester the lecturer provides two assignments consisting of individual assignments and group assignments.
2. Calculate the UTS value of each student
3. Calculate the UAS value of each student
4. Calculating the number of courses in one semester
5. Calculating IPS by adding all assignment values consisting of values1, values2, uts, and extents then divided by the number of courses
6. Calculate the GPA by multiplying 0.10 with IPS
7. Determine the prediction of Bidikmisi student graduation by comparing the number of GPAs that have been calculated with the standard GPA determined by the Purbaya Polytechnic

The following is the course flow of the program:

Flow Chart System

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data used in this study are data from Purbaya Tegal Polytechnic students consisting of determined values.

Table 4.1 Datasheet Sample

NIM	NAME	CLASS	Value 1	Value 2	Exam 1	Exam 2	Total Course	Predictions
1802034	TO'ATIN	C	90	78	85	88	11

The following are the predictive steps of Bidikmisi student graduation with the name TO'ATIN PURBAYA POLYTECHNIC with manual calculation:

A. PASS

1. $(\text{Nilai1} + \text{Nilai2} + \text{UTS} + \text{UAS}) / \text{JMLHMTKL} = \text{IPS}$
2. Jadi, $(80 + 70 + 78 + 85) / 11 = 28.4545$
3. $0.10 * \text{IPS} = \text{IPK}$
4. $0.10 * 28.4545 = 2.84545$

B. NOT PASS

1. $(\text{Nilai1} + \text{Nilai2} + \text{UTS} + \text{UAS}) / \text{JMLHMTKL} = \text{IPS}$
2. Jadi, $(70 + 60 + 72 + 65) / 11 = 24.2727$
3. $0.10 * \text{IPS} = \text{IPK}$
4. $0.10 * 24.2727 = 2.42727$

C. PREDICTIONS

Meet the specified GPA:

1. Final GPA \geq standard GPA
2. Final GPA ≥ 2.70

Does not meet the specified GPA and must repeat one semester:

1. Final GPA \leq standard GPA

2. Final GPA \leq 2.70

So, the prediction of Bidikmisi student graduation with the name TO'AT TIN with nim 1802034 is PASS

The following is a bidikmisi student graduation prediction program

```
main.cpp x
6  {
7      char namamhs[20], kls;
8      double nim, Ips, Ipk;
9      int nilai1, nilai2, uts, uas, jmlhmakul;
10     cout << " " << endl;
11     cout << " " << endl;
12     cout << "-----" << endl;
13     cout << " PREDIKSI KELULUSAN MAHASISWA BIDIKMISI " << endl;
14     cout << " POLITEKNIK PURBAYA " << endl;
15     cout << "-----" << endl;
16     cout << " Masukan nama mahasiswa : "; cin.getline(namamhs, 20);
17     cout << " Masukan nim : "; cin >> nim;
18     cout << " Masukan kelas : "; cin >> kls;
19     cout << "-----" << endl;
20     cout << " SILAHKAN MEMASUKAN NILAI MAHASISWA " << endl;
21     cout << " " << endl;
22     cout << " Masukan Tugas1 : "; cin >> nilai1;
23     cout << " Masukan Tugas2 : "; cin >> nilai2;
24     cout << " Masukan UTS : "; cin >> uts;
25     cout << " Masukan UAS : "; cin >> uas;
26     cout << " Masukan Jumlah Makul : "; cin >> jmlhmakul;
```

Program Source Code

```
27     Ips=nilai1+nilai2+uts+uas;
28     Ipk=0.10*(Ips/jmlhmakul);
29     cout << " IPK anda adalah : " << Ipk;
30     cout << " " << endl;
31     if(Ipk>2.70){
32         cout << " Mahasiswa atas nama " << namamhs << " SELAMAT ANDA LULUS " << endl;
33     }
34     else {
35         cout << " Mahasiswa atas nama " << namamhs << " ANDA TIDAK LULUS (Mengulang 1 Semester)" << endl;
36     }
37     return 0;
38 }
39
40
```

Program Calculations

The following are compiling results from the Bidikmisi student graduation prediction program using code :: block by running the program then entering the text according to what has been specified

```
C:\Users\AngelBeats\Documents\tato\tugas\bin\Debug\tugas.exe
-----
PREDIKSI KELULUSAN MAHASISWA BIDIKMISI
POLITEKNIK PURBAYA
-----
Masukan nama mahasiswa : NINIK
Masukan nim : 1809876
Masukan kelas : C
-----
SILAHKAN MEMASUKAN NILAI MAHASISWA
Masukan Tugas1 : 80
Masukan Tugas2 : 70
Masukan UTS : 70
Masukan UAS : 85
Masukan Jumlah Makul : 11
IPK anda adalah : 2.84545
Mahasiswa atas nama NINIK SELAMAT ANDA LULUS
Process returned 0 (0x0) execution time : 40.830 s
Press any key to continue.
```

Value Pass Result Program

```
C:\Users\AngelBeats\Documents\tato\tugas\bin\Debug\tugas.exe

-----
PREDIKSI KELULUSAN MAHASISWA BIDIKMISI
POLITEKNIK PURBAYA
-----
Masukan nama mahasiswa : CICI
Masukan nim             : 1804056
Masukan kelas           : C
-----
SILAHKAN MEMASUKAN NILAI MAHASISWA
Masukan Tugas1          : 70
Masukan Tugas2          : 60
Masukan UTS             : 72
Masukan UAS             : 65
Masukan Jumlah Makul   : 11
IPK anda adalah : 2.42727
Mahasiswa atas nama CICI ANDA TIDAK LULUS (Mengulang 1 Semester)
Process returned 0 (0x0)   execution time : 29.948 s
Press any key to continue.
```

Value Not Passing Result Program

The calculation is done by looking at the number of values that students have obtained with the provisions divided by the number of courses totaling 11. Then the results are multiplied again by 0.10 to get a comma result which later 2 numbers behind the comma will be used as a benchmark.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above research using the C ++ code-based programming language :: block for predictions of Bidikmisi student graduation from Purbaya Tegal Polytechnic can improve the accuracy of calculation results and time efficiency so that the processing of student data so much can be done more quickly and effectively.

To get a more effective and better predictive result, you can add the Naive Bayes algorithm.

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